

Formation of art history and art studies as a science

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Abstract: In this article, the history of the origin and types of art, people who created in different directions of art, and the formation of art studies as a science are widely covered.

Key words: art, art history, art history, museology, object, function, cinematographer, photography, painting, painting, music.

Art studies is a set of social sciences that study art in a broad sense; studies the artistic culture of the society as a whole and particular types of art, their emergence and laws of development, their uniqueness and relationship to reality, the role of social consciousness in history, the relationship of social life and culture with other processes, the sum of all issues related to the content and form of an artistic work . The science of art studies includes literary studies, museum studies, theater studies, film studies, as well as art studies in the narrow and most commonly used sense, i.e. architecture, painting, sculpture, graphics, applied art, and decorative arts, which are fine (plastic) or spatial arts. includes In particular, he studies many aspects of visual arts, architecture, applied decorative arts, and design. There are such types of art science as art theory, art history and art criticism within the framework of plastic arts. They are interconnected and each has its own special function. Art theory studies the ideological content, artistic form, style, means of expression, special characteristics of art types and genres, and other issues in their interaction with respect to fine art; also considers the general laws, the objective logic of the development of art, its relationship with society, its impact on the community and the individual. Art history studies and researches the general development of art ("general art history") in a country or a particular period, analyzes the development of a type or genre of art, flow, direction, and the creative style of some artists. Art criticism analyzes modern artistic life, examines and evaluates its direction, types and genres, the creativity of some art masters and their individual works of art; compares art phenomena with the ideal of life and social era. Based on these, the main areas and literary genres of art studies are determined: theoretical treatise, manual for artists, theoretical and historical, general and special (monograph) studies, articles and speeches, critical summaries, among others. Uses the method of art studies, social studies and a number of specific sciences; also, due to the fact that the artistic creation is the object of research, it reflects on its aesthetic evaluation, the style of a certain period or the individual taste of the art critic related to these processes.

The scientific activity of art studies is wide and diverse: collecting concrete evidence in the field of study, studying them in detail and summarizing them; types of opening and repair of art monuments with the help of expeditions; identification, registration and regulation of monuments; collecting information about the artist and his works, compiling a catalog of scientific museums, creating biographical and other references, publishing the literary heritage of artists (memoirs, letters, sketches, etc.).

The social importance of art studies, along with the scientific importance of its conclusions and conclusions, is determined by popularizing and promoting art (popular scientific literature, organizing lectures, excursions), attracting a wide readership to the work of art and explaining it. By determining one or another evaluation system in the scope of modern aesthetic principles and in the field of artistic heritage, art science has a deep influence on the creative process of its time.

Art history as a science was formed during the 16th-19th centuries. Before that, it was in the form of philosophical, religious and other disciplines or in the form of a description of some information and manuals. The first examples are Greece (Aristotle, Plato, 4th century BC), Qad. In Rome (Cicero, Vitruvius, 1st century BC - 1st century AD), Asian countries published comprehensive and universal treatises describing many aspects of the theory and history of art. Some instructions for architects and artists, religious mythological legends, philosophical, moral and other ideas, art history elements are described in them. The treatises created in the Middle Ages in the East contained the recommendations of experienced painters and calligraphers, Islamic beliefs and enlightened humanitarian traditions (Sultanali Mashhadi, Dost Muhammad, 16th century), the Renaissance was an important stage in the formation of art history as a science (L. Ghiberti, L. Alberti, Leonardo da Vinci, A. Dürer, etc.), began to stand out as an independent science during the Enlightenment period (French D. Diderot, German G. Lessing, etc.).

In Uzbekistan, art history as a science was formed in the 20s of the 20th century. At first, art criticism developed rapidly; From the 1940s, attention to national culture and its heritage increased, and patriotic ideas were expressed in art. In the 1950s and 1980s, a wide path was opened to topical issues, realistic multifaceted research (B. Nikiforov, L. Jadova, S. Krukovskaya, M. Muns, A. Umarov, R. Toqtosh, D. Fakhretdinova, T. Makhmudov, L. Shostko, A. Hakimov, N. Abdullayev and others). Art historians at the Art History Institute of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan. and new layers of medieval art are being studied (G. Pugachenkova, L. Rempel, P. Zoxidov, Sh. Toshkhojayev, etc.).

Art is a unique form of social consciousness and human activity. Art has an ancient history, and it began to appear in the first stages of the development of society in connection with the labor process and the development of people's social activities. The first traces of primitive art date back to the late Paleolithic period, ca. avv. It dates back to the 20th-40th

millennium. At that time, art had not yet emerged as an independent form of human activity. Because spirituality is material i.ch. was mixed with Later, as a result of the growth of culture, art gradually separated as a separate field. Along with satisfying people's aesthetic requirements, art has served as a means of educating society members in a certain spirit, developing them intellectually and emotionally, expressing their various goals, feelings, interests, and ideals in different periods of its development. Art differs from other forms of social consciousness in terms of its subject, content, way and style of expressing reality, its role and tasks in social life. Art is a product of artistic creativity that shows the knowledge, experience, skills and abilities of a person in his material and spiritual activities. In the history of aesthetic thinking, art has progressed towards the ideas of reflecting things and events as they are and artistic expression of life based on the laws of beauty. Nature, society, and the social, spiritual, and national world of man are the subject of art. No matter how the reality is expressed artistically, the creator reacts to it from the point of view of a certain socio-aesthetic ideal and gives his aesthetic assessment.

The issue of understanding art and determining its place in people's lives has been the cause of serious debates throughout the history of culture. Accordingly, the content of art consists of a unity of objective and subjective, real and imaginary factors. The socio-aesthetic tasks of art are very wide and diverse. Art is a source of aesthetic pleasure for a person; gives beauty to human life; forms an emotional attitude to reality in people; a means of observation, study and knowledge of life; helps to change life in the direction a person dreams of; educational tool; encourages to be inspired by beauty in life, to hate ugliness; a spiritual bridge between people, a means of communication; educates people's artistic and aesthetic taste, forms a certain worldview in them, etc. Art is to a certain extent connected with other phenomena of the spiritual life of society (science, ideology, morality). The purpose of art is to satisfy people's aesthetic needs by creating artistic mastery of the world, creating works that can give people pleasure and enrich them spiritually. The focus of works of art is on people, their social relations and mutual relations, life and activities in certain historical conditions. Therefore, the educational knowledge provided by works of art differs from the information obtained from scientific works about a specific country, nation, or a historical period and individuals. The educational power of art lies in the fact that the experiences and images expressed in it penetrate into the hearts of every student and viewer, and awaken in them feelings of pleasure.

Art, in its various forms, constitutes an aesthetic system that has the ability to collect, store, and transmit unique artistic-aesthetic values to others. The arts include visual arts, architecture, painting, sculpture, music, theater, film, circus, fiction, choreography, and more. Types of art differ from each other in terms of their subject matter, means of representation, and possibilities of expression. For example, language serves as the main

means of expression in literature; in fine art, a concrete emotional image is embodied through paints; in the theater, the image of the characters of the play is reflected in the actors. Art, like all forms of social consciousness, has its own laws of development. While these laws originate from the internal characteristics of art, the level of civilization of the people, nation, people, country and the world, which is related to social development, is expressed in these laws. The laws of art are studied by aesthetics and art science. In a metaphorical sense, high skill inherent in all spheres of activity is understood as "art". For example, the art of argumentation, the art of warfare, the art of leadership, the art of public speaking, etc.

Art history refers to the history of any activity or product made by people for aesthetic, communication, thought, feeling, or worldview purposes. It has been classified differently in different times, for example, in the Middle Ages it was divided into independent and mechanical arts, and later it was divided into elegant and practical-decorative arts; art is now defined as an expression of human creativity. By the 20th century, the major arts included architecture, dance, sculpture, music, painting, poetry (the aesthetic form or function of literature, including theater and narrative), cinematography, and photography. Design and polygraphy arose where plastic and fine arts collided. In addition to ancient forms of artistic expression such as fashion and gastronomy, new arts such as video, computer, advertising, animation, television and video games have emerged. Drawing on several disciplines, art history examines how art changes over time, classifies cultures, divides it into periods, and examines the distinctive and influential characteristics of art. The study of art history dates back to the Renaissance and is limited to Western civilization. However, over time, it came to include the culture of other civilizations, and cultural relativism was born. Today, art benefits from the large-scale research, dissemination and preservation of the artistic heritage of mankind accumulated over history. In the 20th century, the number of art institutes, foundations, museums, and galleries dedicated to the analysis and cataloging of works of art and public exhibitions in both the public and private sectors increased rapidly. The development of communication media has played a decisive role in the study and dissemination of art. International exhibitions such as the Whitney, Venice, São Paulo biennials, documenta in Kassel helped to create new styles and trends. Prizes such as Turner, Wolf, Pritzker, Pulitzer and Oscar have been promoting the best examples of art on an international level. Institutions such as UNESCO are working to preserve important monuments on our planet.

In the 9th century, Fine Art, the creativity of the miniaturists of Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Kokand manifested itself in Central Asia. It is known that the 19th century enlightener, poet, philosopher, and even astronomer Ahmad Donish (1827-1897) also had the talent of an artist. This is evidenced by his paintings that have reached us: "Poet and Artist" miniature dedicated to Abduqadir Bedil's "Four Elements" manuscript and a

satirical miniature depicting the city's mirshab. The miniatures drawn by him are distinguished by a perfect finished picture, replaced paints, clear and smooth counter lines, his graphic signature. Ahmad Donish's student Abdulkhaliq Mahmud is also known as an artist who skillfully depicts insects and flowers. Horse and deer figurines carved by Tokhta Sadiq Khojayev from Tashkent with his own hands, without any sculpting tools or cuts, in simple pen carving. The fact that it was displayed at the Turkestan Exhibition in 1886 is evidence of the desire of the peoples of Central Asia to reflect existence in artistic images. At the same exhibition, models of houses made by craftsmen from Tashkent were displayed: a two-story European-style house made of ganch and two Uzbek houses, which were made like real ones with great skill.

The famous Uzbek engraver Tashpolat Arslonkulov (1882-1962) made bas-relief-medallions with the portraits of A.V. Suvorov and M.I. Kutuzov using photographs in the building of the Military Council (Officers' House) in Tashkent. In 1915, Tashkent lithography published the epic "Son of the Grave" with illustrations by artist Sirojiddin Makhsum Siddiqi. This is the only Uzbek artist whose work was associated with printing in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. In the 70s of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the works of Russian artists, mainly students of the St. Petersburg Academy of Arts, took place in the visual arts of Turkestan. Their art reflects the history and era of Central Asia, nature and life. V. V. Vereshchagin was the first and influential artist who reflected the life and everyday life of Turkestan in his work. His paintings on the theme of Turkestan made this country a truly artistic discovery for many countries and peoples. In the Turkestan series, the artist reflected the country's cultural and household lifestyle in his comprehensive and multifaceted paintings, imbued with the spirit of humanity. In a number of his works, he demonstrated the high construction culture and excellent decorative skills of Central Asian architects and folk crafts. It can be noted that at the beginning of the 20th century, the appearance of teachers-artists teaching painting and drawing in secondary schools in Turkestan indicated that the first buds of visual art and visual literacy began to sprout in the country. This contributed to the establishment of the artistic environment in Turkestan.

Sergey Petrovich Yudin (1858-1933), a famous Tashkent painter, led the theater circle of railway workers, and also painted decorations for amateur theaters in Tashkent. He came to Tashkent in 1902 after graduating from the Petersburg Art Academy. S. Yudin is a master of sunny plein air etudes. The traditional landscape has become extremely popular with landscape paintings painted in the color image style. In S.Yudin's "Winter Evening" landscape, created in 1910, one can feel the artist's direct communication with nature and his excellent skills in depicting a clear perspective. In his mountain and valley landscapes, a wide space, the play of light and shadow are extremely clearly and vividly reflected. Leonard Leonardovich Bure (1887-1943) from Samarkand was interested in painting from

an early age. In 1904, he went to Moscow, where he studied painting, and then continued his studies at the Art Academy in St. Petersburg. After receiving his education, he returned to his native land and taught at the Samarkand School of Art until the end of his life. Bure limited himself to painting etudes from nature in landscape painting. His architectural scenes were distinguished by the truthfulness of the colors and the elegant sense of colors. Bure tried not to fall into a mold when choosing a perspective on an architectural monument, always looking for new aspects. The collection includes three architectural landscapes: "Labihovuz" from 1907, "Madrasa Yard" from 1910, and "Samarkand" from 1929, which was acquired by the gallery last year. The artist painted them in his favorite cities - Bukhara and Samarkand. The life and work of Alexander Nikolayevich Volkov (1886-1957), one of the most famous artists in Uzbekistan, a master of color rendering and poet, was connected with Fergana. The People's Artist of Uzbekistan was born in Fergana, studied at the St. Petersburg Academy of Arts, and taught at the technical school of painting in Tashkent.

Although A. Volkov followed the traditions of Russian artists, he also mastered the experience of French cubists. He lived with the idea of finding his own style in painting. Volkov strove to combine the unique color-image structure, the unique rhythms and colorful paints of the East with the methods of the "Paris School" of the first quarter of the 20th century. A. Volkov's social status in the period from 1916 to 1928 is evidenced by the fact that the subjects of his pictures consisted of a teahouse, camel caravans, the old city, and so on. He depicted these themes and subjects in the direction of cubism and expressionism. The painting "Pomegranate Teahouse" stored in the Tretyakov Gallery was painted in 1924, when he was interested in cubism. In 1968, this picture was shown in Paris, which caused wide comments by the Parisian press, and was also shown on French television. The painting "Autumn landscape" kept in the bank's collection was painted in the impressionist style in 1931, in which color and light are intricately modified with great skill. The artist Aleksandr Vladimirovich Nikolayev, who entered the history of the visual arts of Uzbekistan under the name of Master Momin (1897-1957), also fell in love with the ancient culture and rich folk art of Central Asia.

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